

TEACHERS' OPINIONS ON UNETHICAL CONDUCTS OF EDUCATION ADMINISTRATORS

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to determine teachers' opinions on unethical conducts of education administrators and on individual or organizational reflections of such behaviours in terms of various independent variables. The study is a qualitative study with a holistic multiple-case pattern. The study group of the study consisted of 10 teachers who were employed in official training-education institutions located in Kepez District, Antalya Province and voluntarily participated in the study. Interview data were attempted to be analysed using descriptive and content analysis methods. It was determined as a result of the study that education administrators were in unethical conducts. Furthermore, it was found out that unethical conducts of education administrators had negative effects on organizational structure and functioning and that ethical conducts of education administrators increased organizational and academic success and positively affected organizational commitment.

Keywords: administrative ethics, unethical conducts, education administrator, teacher

1. Introduction

From past to present, behaviours of education administrators in every institution, especially in schools, are crucial regarding to have an impact on structure and functioning of institution. Behaviours of education administrators are important because they affect roles and behaviours of employers and students, and all stakeholders in broader sense. First of all, this importance is due to the fact that an education administrator has undertaken training-educational activities in institutions like schools and is the most effective and competent person in an institution that aims to give desired behaviours. It then is due to the fact that education administrators must be

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role models as an authority figure both for teachers and students whom are directly influenced by education (Pehlivan, 1997).

It is one of the most primary duties of a management to ensure that organization develops in line with scientific and social values by using all resources effectively and efficiently (Taymaz, 2015). It is observed that education administrators face with making moral choices when doing their daily routines in their institutions (Beck, Murphy & Associates, 1997) and that they often decide with their moral values due to the absence of ethical principles determined. It has been determined in many studies that education administrators are influenced by their personal values and ethics in their decisions and actions (Pehlivan, 1998; Begley & Leithwood, 1990; Marshall, 1992; Kasten & Ashbaugh, 1991; Winter, Newton & Kirkpatrick, 1998).

Work to be carried out by education administrators should become integrated with the values of the democratic society and be shaped by universal ethical principles. Tolerating different cultures and ideas, respecting all individuals of society, equality of individuals and equitable distribution of resources underlie ethical principles (Gronn, 1999).

The word "Ethics" derives from the word "Ethos", which means "character", "custom", "method" or "tradition" in Greek. The investigation of the basis of all human behaviours and actions is the sphere of interest of ethics (Mengüşoğlu, 1965).

Education administrators must act in accordance with professional ethical principles as well as laws and regulations when performing their duties. Francis and Armstrong (2003) list seven principles that guide ethical conduct as follows;

- Respect,
- Equality,
- Care,
- Honesty,
- Openness,
- Tolerance,
- Avoiding suffering harm.

The administrator must develop a chain of ethical principles based on the values of the community and share it with other employees. The administrator is also required to lead ethically. Unethical conducts are observed in schools in different ways. Improper hiring by the administrator of his/her relatives, procuring students to pass their classes although they do not deserve, accepting mutual gifts, oral and bodily harassment, discrimination based on race, language and religion, embezzlement of school money, use of one's own career to cause somebody's fall, abuse of work may serve as the samples of unethical conducts that can be seen in schools. School administrators have a huge responsibility in school administration. The education administrator must, at every opportunity, orally emphasise the school's ethical principles both to employees and students at the centre of education and be the practitioner of those principles. Ethical principles determined in school must be applied equally to all employees and to students who continue their education (Aydn, 2001).

The education administrator who aims to develop his/her organization must act within the framework of ethical principles when using human and material resources effectively and efficiently and try to form an organizational culture by increasing organizational commitment, and by ensuring organizational socialization, of the organization's employees.

The education administrator who has goals to increase organizational commitment by remaining within the framework of ethical principles should start considering the definitions of organizational commitment in literature. Organizational commitment is defined as the strong desire of individuals to adopt organizational goals and values and to maintain organizational membership (Hunt & Morgan, 1994; Chang & Chelladurai, 2003). In his study conducted in 2004, Çöl defined organizational commitment as the measure of the desire of employees to integrate with, and embrace the principles, goals and values of, the organization in which they work, strive for organizational gains and continue working in the organization. Organizational commitment is one of the basic activities and the ultimate goals of organizations' efforts to maintain their presence, because individuals with organizational commitment are more adaptive, have higher job satisfaction, are more productive, work with the sense of high commitment and responsibility and cost less in the organization (Balci, 2003, Halis, 2010).

Increased organizational commitment will also contribute to socialization. The process in which an individual cease to be a biological asset and is integrated into a certain society and clusters is called socialization. With this process, the individual gains attitudes that enable him/her to live in a society and acquires a character (Ozankaya, 1999).

Organizational socialization encompasses the replacement of the former attitudes and values with new attitudes and values in an organization as well as the learning of tools, responsibilities, organizational values and rules required to achieve the goals of the organization. In fact, organizational socialization is about learning of organizational culture and adapting to organizational culture (Çelik, 1997).

Education administrators have the most important duty in the process of in-house socialization of teachers who are employees of school. The education administrator has a great influence on the character of the school, who is responsible for the implementation of the curriculum that coordinates the functioning of the school. The education administrator has a critical importance in the development of the social and academic climate of the school (Balci, 2003).

It is inevitable that an organization with increased organizational commitment and realized socialization will develop its culture. Organizational culture is a systematic whole of the meaning and characteristics that are shared by the members of the organization and distinguish it from other organizations (Özkalp, 1995). School culture is defined as rules, beliefs, and values that guide the conducts of administrators, teachers and students in a school (Richard, 1999).

It is possible to say that unethical conducts of education administrators may impair organizational structure and functioning, interfere with the communication

between employees and cause conflicts between other education stakeholders and the organization, in addition to their positive effects on the organizational commitment of the employees and the organizational culture of the organization. In this respect, it can be emphasized that education administrators should avoid unethical conducts, in addition to their adherence to ethical principles.

Unethical conducts refer to conflicts, aggressive behaviours and behavioural problems that occur in the organization for various reasons. Unethical conducts affect the quality of organizational life, motivation, performance, commitment and satisfaction of employees negatively no matter for what reason and at what level they occur (Özdevecioğlu & Aksoy, 2005). Unethical conducts are interpersonal behaviours that cause disruption of generally accepted social rules of conduct (Lefkowitz, 2006).

Unethical conducts arise both from individual and organizational reasons. Examination of the literature on unethical conducts will reveal that there are two main types of such conducts in general.

A. Social-Cultural and Economic Types:

- Discrimination,
- Favouritism,
- Corruption,
- Bribe,
- Subservience and use of familiarity,
- Bigotry-fanaticism,
- Repressive acts and misguiding.

B. Psychological Types:

- Mobbing and bullying,
- Selfishness,
- Torture,
- Violence and repression,
- Physical and sexual harassment,
- Dogmatic behaviours (Gül, 2006).

In this context, the purpose of this study is to determine whether or not school administrators have a tendency to unethical conducts according to opinions of teachers employed in official educational institutions and identify teachers' opinions concerning individual and organizational reflections of such tendencies on organizational commitment, academic success, organizational success, organizational culture and organizational socialization should school administrators have a tendency to unethical conducts. Within the framework of this basic problem, answers to the following questions will be sought;

1. What are the opinions of teachers about unethical conducts in administration?
2. What are the opinions of teachers about the factors that cause unethical conducts of education administrators?
3. What are the opinions of teachers about the effects of unethical conducts of education administrators on organizational culture, organizational commitment and organizational socialization?

4. What are the opinions of teachers about the impact of ethical and unethical conducts of education administrators on organizational and academic success?
5. What and why do teachers compare the concept of ethics?

2. Method

Below is the model of the study, study group, data collection tools and analysis of the data.

2.1 Study Model

This study is a qualitative study. Qualitative studies have been defined by Yıldırım and Şimşek (2006) as the studies in which qualitative data collection methods, such as observation, interview and document analysis, are used and in which a process of revealing perceptions and events in a realistic and holistic manner in natural environment is followed. The method used in this study is case study method, one of the qualitative study methods, and is in a holistic multiple case design. Yin (1984) described the case study as a study method that investigated the case within his/her own framework of life and that was used in cases where the boundaries between the case and his/her environment were not clearly drawn with certain lines and where more than one evidence or data source was available.

The easy-to-access sampling technique, one of the purposeful sampling methods, was used in the study, which is often used for qualitative studies. This sampling method allows for studying of situations that are considered to have rich knowledge. It provides quick access to data. The purposeful sampling is useful in most instances to reveal and explain cases and events (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2011).

2.2 Data Collection Tool and Collection of Data

A conceptual framework for the interview questions was determined by screening the literature on unethical conducts of education administrators in order to obtain the study data, and semi-structured questions were prepared to be asked during interviews with teachers in accordance with the purpose of the study. A semi-structured interview form was created with five (5) questions developed by the researchers. Two (2) educational sciences experts and one (1) language expert expressed their opinions on the interview form prepared, and the preliminary implementation was started based on the opinions of these experts. During the preliminary implementation, feedbacks were obtained from the teachers about the clarity of the questions, the interview questions were reviewed and then, it was preceded with the implementation stage upon the approval of the experts.

The participant teachers were contacted during the implementation stage of the study and a suitable day and time was determined and an appointment was made to conduct the study. The teachers were informed about the study by the researchers on the date determined, and interviews were conducted with the semi-structured interview form consisting of five (5) questions. The interviews with the participants

lasted between 15 and 20 minutes. The interviews were recorded using mobile phones' voice recording feature to better analyse the data obtained from the interviews and save time. The interviews recorded were later translated into text.

2.3 Analysis of Data

Names of the participants were not disclosed and were kept confidential by the researchers for the participant teachers to answer the questions sincerely. A coding system in the form of A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, I, J was preferred when quoting the opinions of the participants.

Data collected by the researchers were transcribed and analysed using descriptive analysis and content analysis techniques, which are the analysis techniques used in qualitative study methods. The purpose of descriptive analysis is to translate raw data into a format so that readers can understand and use them if desired. Data obtained from the descriptive analysis are summarized and interpreted according to previously determined themes. In this analysis, direct quotations are frequently included to conspicuously reflect the opinions of the individuals interviewed or observed (Altunışık & Others, 2001; Yıldırım & Şimsek, 2005). Content analysis encompasses four stages, being processing of qualitative study data obtained, coding of data, finding of themes, arranging of codes and themes, defining and interpreting of findings (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2006). Content analysis is used to define data and to reveal hidden facts in the data (Gülbahar & Alper, 2009). The arithmetic mean of the Cohen kappa coefficient was found as .90 as a result of the calculation of the consistency ratio of the themes identified by the researchers in the analysis process of the data. The Kappa coefficient between 0.00 and .20 is interpreted as no consistency; between .21 and .40 as moderate consistency; between .41 and .60 general consistency; between .61 and .80 as significant consistency; and between .81 and 1.00 as perfect consistency (Landis & Koch, 1977). It was decided that the theme codes were reliable since it was understood that there had been a perfect consistency between the evaluators as a result of the arithmetic mean of this Kappa coefficient.

2.4 Study Group

The study group consisted of 10 (ten) teachers who were selected on a voluntary basis among from the teachers employed in the official education institutions in Kepez District, Antalya Province during the first semester of the 2017-2018 Academic Year, in accordance with the holistic multi-case pattern. Information on the participants is given in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Information on Participants

Code	Gender	Branch	Age	Seniority (Year)
A	Female	Physical Education	35	9
B	Female	Classroom	50	20
C	Female	Classroom	49	27
D	Female	Classroom	31	7
M	Female	Classroom	45	20
F	Male	Turkish	39	13

G	Male	Turkish	34	12
H	Male	Physical Education	38	17
I	Male	Special Education	32	8
J	Male	Classroom	34	13

As seen in Table 1, 50% of the participants are male teachers and 50% female teachers. Also, the branch of the half of the participants is classroom teaching, and all the participants are aged above 30. The ratio of teachers with a service year of above 10 years is 70%. Furthermore, teachers from 5 different branches participated in the study.

3. Findings

3.1 Findings related to sub-problem

Table 2 below includes the frequency and percentage values including the teachers' opinions on unethical conducts in administration:

Table 2: Teachers' Opinions on Unethical Conducts in Administration

Sub-Theme	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	f	(%)
Mobbing					√	√		√			3	30
Favouritism and Discrimination	√			√			√		√	√	5	50
Interest		√	√	√		√	√	√			6	60
Rapport and Subservience		√						√			2	20
Exclusion									√		1	10

As it is seen in Table 2, examination of the opinions of the participating teachers about the unethical conducts in administration shows that the theme Interest ranks the first with the rate of 60%, and the theme Exclusion ranks the last with the ratio of 10%. It is seen that the participating classroom teachers and the branch teachers express the theme Interest at the rate of 60%. Some of the participating teachers' opinions in this regard are given below:

"In my opinion, the first one of the unethical conducts of the school administrators is individual characteristics and the second is syndical characteristics. I think that problems rather increase with appointments made due to the placement of people without administrative ability in the school administration just for personal interests." (D1, 3).

"I think there are two parties to this. Some people want to be, and keep themselves, closer to administration. if they do so, I guess they think that they would be more comfortable in certain dealings. Some administrators want to keep themselves close to teachers so they will try to obtain information from them about the course of the school or something similar. Neither being close to the administration, nor attempts by the administration to keep teachers close to itself are ethical conducts" (B1, 4).

"We experience threats, blackmailing, oppression, and psychological pressure by administrators, in other words, the problems which are common in every society and in every institution today. Of course, our friends experience the same, as well" (E1, 1).

"In my opinion, unethical conducts occur when an administrator favours the people from his/her union or is one step closer to fellow townsmen, people from his/her own province, county" (G1, 2).

"Let me emphasize again, unethical conducts may be union-related and/or related to being from the same home-town or may arise from reflecting external social relationships to the school, or the opposite the foregoing, or exclusion due to membership to a different union" (I1, 5).

3.2 Findings related to sub-problem

Table 3 below includes the frequency and percentage values including the teachers' opinions on the factors that cause unethical conducts of education administrators:

Table 3: Teachers' Opinions about the Factors that Cause Unethical Conducts of Education Administrators

Sub-Theme	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	f	(%)
Incompetence			√	√		√		√	√		5	50
Personality		√	√	√	√		√	√			6	60
Trade Union				√					√	√	3	30
Preserving the office						√	√			√	3	30
Personal and Social Relations	√								√		2	20
Self-Interests				√						√	2	20

As seen in Table 3, examination of the opinions of the participating teachers about the factors that cause unethical conducts of education administrators reveals that the theme Personality ranks the first with the ratio of 60%; the theme Personal and Social Relations and the theme Self Interests rank the last with the ratio of 20%. According to Table 3, it is clear that the branch teachers have expressed their opinions on the theme Preserving the Office with the ratio of 30% while the participating classroom teachers have expressed their opinions on the theme Personality with the ratio of 80%. Some of the participating teachers' opinions in this regard are given below:

"Let us think for our own country. Some of school administrators deserve their positions, and some of not. Those who do not deserve their positions put pressure on their colleagues and teacher friends because they do not deserve their positions, in other words, they are not competent" (F2, 1).

"I think this is rather about the personality of the person in the institution. We do equip ourselves with training and education; however, I think that institution administrators sometimes fail to shape their personalities and to equip themselves in education" (B2, 2).

"Unethical conducts of school administrators vary by person. Teacher's conducts, personal relationship between them, teacher's doings and positive work, all of them can lead to unethical conducts" (A2, 5).

"I think this is all about the character of that administrator in the first place. In other words, if his/her character permits, that is, if it permits to favour and show preferential treatment and if this exists in his/her personality, this the main reason for unethical conducts. Apart from that, he/she may be concerned about preserving his/her office. Such behaviours can lead an administrator to act unethically" (G2, 4).

"The reasons for an administrator to fail to comply with ethical rules may be trade union differences and gender discrimination and/or similar matters" (J2, 3).

"If you ask in terms of the interests of the institution, he/she would say that he/she acted unethically for the interests of the institution, which I believe to be the reason thereof. He/she acts unethically for the interests of the institution or for his/her own interests. Unethical conducts may arise therefrom" (J2, 6).

3.3 Findings related to sub-problem

Table 4 below includes the frequency and percentage values including the teachers' opinions about the effects of unethical conducts of education administrators on organizational culture, organizational commitment and organizational socialization:

Table 4: Teachers' Opinions about the Effects of Unethical Conducts of Education Administrators on Organizational Culture, Organizational Commitment and Organizational Socialization

Sub-Theme	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	f	(%)
Grouping				√	√		√	√	√		5	50
Low Motivation	√	√	√		√		√				5	50
Lack of Communication						√					1	10
Decreased Commitment	√	√				√		√	√	√	6	60
Inefficiency		√	√								2	20

As seen in Table 4, examination of the opinions of the participating teachers about the effects of unethical conducts of education administrators on organizational culture, organizational commitment and organizational socialization reveals that the theme Decreased Commitment ranks the first with the ratio of 60% and the theme Lack of Communication ranks the last with the ratio of 10%. 80% of the participating male teachers expressed their opinions on the theme Decreased Commitment, while 80% of the participating female teachers expressed their opinions on the theme Low Motivation. Some of the participating teachers' opinions in this regard are given below:

"Groupings can be seen in teachers' room. Groupings can occur between school staff. Some say that they are men of the administration, and some say that they are not. These are all the situations caused by ethical events" (I3, 1).

"Of course, they all affect each other very much. They are all connected to each other. First and foremost, success and motivation falls" (E3, 2).

"I think that productivity decreases because unethical conducts of education administrators break the spirit to work and creates insecurity. I think that unethical conducts of school administrators break the spirit of the teachers, employees and people working in any fields within the school and cause decreased productivity in the classroom or working environment. Again, similarly" (C3,5).

"I believe that if we compare socialization to a chain or beads, it will break off because the thread or string that connects the string of beads is the link and socialization. I believe that this link will break off from time to time in terms of communication tools as well as the communication between teachers when education administrators treat any teacher, member to trade union X, and any other teacher, member to trade union Y, differently than each other, that teachers will side against each other and that teachers will break off the communication not only with the administration, but also their friends of different opinions" (F3, 3).

"Their confidence in that institution in terms of organizational commitment may reduce. A person who thinks that the administrator acts unethically may lose his/her commitment to the school. He/she would not feel like going to the school by plodding along one step forward two steps back when he/she is coming to the school in the morning or any other time. This will also negatively affect the school culture" (I3, 4).

3.4 Findings related to sub-problem

Table 5 below includes the frequency and percentage values including the teachers' opinions about the effect of ethical and unethical conducts of education administrators on organizational and academic success:

Table 5: Teachers' Opinions about the Effect of Ethical and Unethical Conducts of Education Administrators on Organizational and Academic Success

Sub-Theme	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	f	(%)
Academic and Organizational Success	√		√	√	√		√	√	√	√	8	80
Responsibility						√					1	10
Productivity				√	√						2	20
Organizational Commitment				√		√	√			√	4	40
Positive and Negative Feelings		√			√	√	√	√			5	50

As seen in Table 5, examination of the opinions of the participating teachers about the effect of ethical conducts of education administrators on organizational and academic success reveals that the theme Academic and Organizational Success ranks the first with the ratio of 80% and the theme Responsibility ranks the last with the ratio of 10%. According to Table 5, 80% of the participating female teachers and 80% of the participating male teachers expressed their opinions on the theme Academic and Organizational Success. Some of the participating teachers' opinions in this regard are given below:

"Acting ethically will, of course, increase the success of the institution. I think that all of them will be affected, because school, teacher, student can move forward and be successful all together" (A4, 1).

"I think that contented employees, contented students, contented-respectful happy teachers, happy-successful, moral students will bring a happy society" (C4, 5).

"I think this is a factor that directly affects school success, at least in terms of teachers' productivity. I think that the more the teacher feels himself/herself belong to the school and the more the teacher is committed to the school, the more he/she will be productive" (D4, 3).

"As I have said, the eagerness to work and success of everyone will increase if administrators obtain collective opinions in matters concerning the school, act ethically, treat everyone equally and comply with rules, like parents taking their children to a park at a weekend to make them happy when we consider the administrator as the head of the family. In this way, the success of the organization as well as the commitment of both teachers and students to the organization will increase and become more positive" (J4, 4).

"Teachers will do their best to achieve justice at the highest possible level, have a sense of belonging and responsibility and reflect them to their students, and students will be able to express and manage themselves better in an environment of justice and thus, will make clearer decisions" (F4, 2).

3.5 Findings related to sub-problem

In this sub-problem, teachers were asked to compare the concept of ethics to anything, explain the reason of this comparison, and findings obtained related thereto are grouped in Table 6.

Table 6: Metaphors on the Concept of Ethics

Sub-Theme	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	f	(%)
Object and Article	√	√		√		√	√	√	√	√	8	80
Nature			√								1	10
Other					√						1	10

Examination of the participating teachers' opinions on the metaphor question of the study "To what and why do teachers compare the concept of ethics? showed that 80% compared the concept of ethics to an '**Object and Article**', 10% to a concept associated with '**Nature**', and 10% to '**Other**', apart from the foregoing. 100% of the participating male teachers compared the concept of ethics to the metaphors of '**Object and Article**'. 60% of the participating female teachers compared the concept of ethics to the metaphors of '**Object and Article**', and the remaining 40% to the metaphors in the '**Nature**' and '**Other**' groups in equal proportions of 20%. The participant teacher A compared the concept of ethics to "**Play Doughs**". When he/she was asked about the reason thereof, he/she explained: *"Because I think that you will get a positive result and success if you give a good form to play doughs, but if you fail, you cannot act ethically and accordingly, the return will be negative"*. The participant teacher B compared the concept of ethics to a "**Ball**" and explained the reason: *"I compare it to a ball with two faces different than each other like a ball with one side red and the other side pink. I thought that the colour of those who act unethically would be red which reflects blushing, while the colour of those who comply with ethical rules would be pink which reflect good, pureness, honesty"*. The participant teacher C described the concept of ethics as "**Sky**" and explained the reason: *"I have said sky because it is colourful, but pure and clean and gives you the feeling of peace and freedom when you look at and see it harmoniously, but it is also harmonious in those colours in such a crowd."* According to participant teacher D, the concept of ethics resembles "**Wood**". When he/she was asked about the reason, she explained: *"I compare it to wood because wood will never change outside and inside no matter what you do with it, no matter what form you give to it. So, the concept of ethics is something like that at least for me. I mean that it will never change how a human being looks like, although some changes occur in his/her body"*. The participant teacher E compared the concept of ethics to a "**Ghost**", a metaphor listed in the metaphor group "**Other**", by explaining: *"The question 'Do ethics exist?' should be asked first. Do ethics exist? Do ethics survive? Ethics is a ghost for me now, something that does not exist. Ethics is something that can no longer be found in the community."* The participant teacher F compared the concept of ethics to "**Water or Dough**" and explained: *"I compare it to water or dough because ethics or moral are the concepts that change over time in the society. A concept that is regarded ethical in Turkish society today may not be find ethical in the future. In addition, ethics and moral are the concepts that can change on a universal scale and depending on time, and because water and dough change and take the form of the container and hand in which they are."* The participant teacher G compared the concept of ethics to the metaphor "**Water**" and explained: *"I compare it to water, because the concept which we call ethics should be pure and transparent like water"*. The participant teacher H compared the concept of ethics to a "**Flower**" and explained: *"I compare it to water. I mean if we say nice words, give nutrients and water as it should be, a flower will blossom more and grow better, but if we behave differently time to time, act unethically, for example, if we give water of 150 g where we should give of 50 g, if we give fertilizer of 50 g where we should give of 200 g, the flower will no longer be a flower."* The participant teacher I compared the concept of ethics to a "**Book**" and explained: *"I would compare the concept of ethics to a book if I am asked to compare because books do not reflect their ideologies, but they leave good thoughts to the history*

of humanity and to the future of mankind. If a book tells about its own evil in ideological sense, it would be bad and it would be out of ethics". The participant teacher I compared the concept of ethics to a "Glass" and explained the reason for his/her metaphor: "I compare the concept of ethics to a glass. Why? Because a glass becomes a water glass if you put water in it, becomes a tea glass if you put tea in it, becomes an ayran glass if you put ayran in it, that is to say that what we put in it are our ethical values. They are right for us. However, it would not be tasty to put tea in a water glass, and water should be drunk from a water glass and tea from a tea glass."

4. Conclusion, Discussion and Recommendations

This study investigated the opinions of teachers working in official education institutions about unethical conducts of education administrators appointed in their organizations and about individual and organizational reflections of such conducts in terms of various independent variables.

In this study, 60% of the classroom teachers concluded that unethical conducts in administration were about relations of interest, while 60% of the branch teachers described such conducts as Favouritism and Discrimination. These findings are consistent with the views in the study, performed by Küçükkaraduman in 2006 on education institutions, that primary school principals are not considered qualified by primary school classroom and branch teachers in implementing ethical principles, such as "granting rewards to those who deserve", "treating individuals equally" and "applying rules to everyone equally", in the practices of school administration.

According to the participating teachers, when the factors causing unethical conducts of education administrators are examined, it can be said that the theme Personality stands out with the ratio of 60% and the theme Incompetence with the ratio of 50%. It can be said that the reason that 100% of the classroom teachers and 30% of the branch teachers participated in the study agreed on the themes Personality and Incompetence is due to the fact that these two themes causing unethical conducts are more common in primary school administrators. Çınkır stated in his study (2010) that principals considered the non-observation of the principles of merit in appointments of school principals as a problem and advised as a solution proposal that administrations should transfer resources to schools based on the number of students in schools and that principals should be supported for postgraduate education in the field of educational administration as the most important support strategy. It is anticipated that such a proposal will reduce the factors that cause unethical conducts in administration.

That 80% of the participating female teachers agreed on low motivation can be interpreted as that they refer to the individual reflection of unethical conducts of education administrators, and that 80% of the participating male teachers agreed on reduced commitment can be interpreted as that they refer to the organizational reflection of unethical conducts of education administrators. Ethical perceptions of employees are important because they influence organizational effectiveness and productivity. Environments with no organizational ethics can damage human relations

and undermine intra-organizational trust (Demircan, 2003). According to Karataş and Gül (2010), the most significant factor in the formation of organizational commitment is the willingness of teachers to work for school's success, which is followed by working with the awareness of responsibility and increased motivation by positive work experiences. It has been found out in the doctoral dissertation by Uğurlu (2009) that ethical leadership behaviours of administrators create organizational commitment for teachers in their relations with their schools.

That the participating female and male teachers agreed at the rate of 80% that Academic and Organizational Success would be affected positively or negatively by ethical and unethical conducts of education administrators can be interpreted as that there are no differences of opinion between the participant male and female teachers. According to Uğurlu (2012), unethical conducts of administrators should be questioned because a significant difference between female and male employees of an organization will adversely affect the nature of the climate of that organization. Gülcan, Kılınç and Çepni (2012) did not find any differences between the opinions of male and female teachers in their study, which overlaps with the result of this study.

When the metaphors produced by the teachers, education employers, about the concept of ethics are evaluated in general, it is seen that the comparisons are grouped under three groups, being object and article, nature and other. It is noteworthy that there are comparisons that can be shaped like "Play Dough", "Dough", "Wood" or that take the form of the container in which they are like "Water", produced in the Object and Article Group. With the metaphor "Flower", some teachers refer to that ethical conducts will grow and reproduce the flower, while unethical conducts will wilt the flower, which metaphor can be interpreted as flower care, and that ethical conducts will promote development. With the metaphor "Book", some teachers mean that the concept of ethics is teaching, but also impartial when teaching. With the metaphor "Ball" with one side red and the other side white, some teachers refer to the distinctiveness of the concept of ethics. With the metaphor "Glass" produced, some teachers mean that the concept of ethics should not vary from person to person. With the metaphor "Sky" produced in the group "Nature", some teachers' mention of the contributions by the concept of ethics to the atmosphere of the working environment by creating a harmony in chaos. With this metaphor, it can be said that the concept of ethics arises the sense of freedom in employees. With the metaphor "Ghost" produced in the group "Other", it is indicated that some teachers believe that education administrators never comply with ethical principles and never exhibit ethical conducts.

Based on the findings obtained from the study, the following suggestions have been developed.

Suggestions for practitioners:

- Ethical committees in which all internal and external stakeholders will be represented should be created.
- The principle of merit should be taking into account when appointing education administrators. Priority should be given to the appointment of teachers with masters and doctorate degrees to the position of education administrator.

- Education administrators should not treat some employees preferentially for reasons such as political, ethnic, gender, religious or regional differences.
- Education administrators should not act in contravention of ethical rules neither for their own interests, nor should their institutions' interests and comply with ethical rules and serve as an example when fulfilling their duties.

Suggestions for researchers:

- This study should be investigated by taking the opinions of parents, students and school administrators apart from teachers.
- This study can also be conducted by employing the quantitative study technique.
- This study can be investigated by taking the opinions of the teachers in rural areas as well as teachers in central areas and by comparing their opinions.

References

1. Altunışık, R., Coşkun, R., Yıldırım, E & Bayraktaroğlu, S. (2001). Research Methods in Social Sciences. Adapazarı: Sakarya Bookstore.
2. Aydın, P. İ. (2001). Managerial Professional and Organizational Ethics. Ankara: Pegema Publishing.
3. Balcı, A. (2003). Organizational Socialization Theory Strategy and Tactics. Ankara: Pegema Publishing.
4. Beck, L. G., Murphy, J., & Associates. (1999). *Ethics in Educational Leadership Program: Emerging Models*. Colombia, MO: The University Council For Educational Administration.
5. Begley, P. T., & Leithwood, K. A. (1990). The Influence of Values on School Administration Practices. *Journal of Personnel Evaluation in Education*, 3, 337-352.
6. Chang, K. & Chelladurai, P. (2003). Comparison of Part-Time Workers and Full-Time Workers: Commitment and Citizenship Behaviors in Korean Sport Organization. *Journal of Sport Management*, 17, 394-416.
7. Çelik, V. (1997). School Culture and Management. Ankara: Pegema Publishing.
8. Çinkır, S. (2010). Problems of principals in elementary school: Problem sources and support strategies. *Elementary Online*, 9 (3), 1027-1036.
9. Çöl, G. (2004). The Relationship between Human Resources Organizational Commitment and Similar Concepts. *Journal of Industrial Relations and Human Resources*, 6 (2), 4-11.
10. Demircan, N. (2003). The Impact of Organizational Trust on Organizational Commitment as an Intermediate Variable: An Application in the Education Sector (Unpublished Doctoral Thesis). Gebze University, Kocaeli.
11. Francis, R. & Armstrong, A. (2003). "Ethics as a Risk Management Strategy: The Australian Experience", *Journal of Business Ethics*, 45, 375-385.
12. Gronn, P. (1999). *The Making of Educational Leaders*. Great Britain: Tj International ltd.

13. Gül, H. (2006). "Unethical Behaviors and Their Practice: An Application in State Hospitals". Selçuk University Karaman İ.İ.B.F. Journal (10), 65-79.
14. Gülbahar, Y. & Alper, A. (2009). Researches in the field of instructional technology. Ankara University Journal of Educational Sciences, 42 (2), 93-111.
15. Gülcan, M.G. Kılınç, A.Ç. & Çepni, O. (2012). An Analysis of the Levels of Ethical Leadership Behaviors in Elementary Schools in Terms of Variable Variables. Turkish Journal of Educational Sciences, 10 (1), 123-142.
16. Halis, M. (2010). The Effect of Teachers in Elementary Schools on Organizational Commitment of Job Difficulties. Dumlupınar University Journal of Social Sciences (26), 251-266.
17. Hunt, S.D. & Morgan, R.M. (1994). Organizational Commitment: One of Many Commitments or Key Mediating Construct? *The Academy of Management Journal*, 37 (6), 1568-1587.
18. Karataş, S. & Güleş, H. (2010). "The Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Organizational Connectivity of Primary School Teachers". Uşak University Journal of Social Sciences, 3 (2), 74-89.
19. Kasten, K. L., & Ashbaugh, C. R. (1991). The Place of Values in Superintendent's Work. *Journal of Educational Administration* (29), 54-66.
20. Küçükkaraduman, E. (2006). Investigation of Ethical Behaviors of Primary School Principals (Unpublished masters thesis). Gazi University, Ankara.
21. Landis, J. R. & Koch, G. G. (1977). The measurement of observer agreement for categorical. *Biometrics*, 33, 159-174.
22. Lefkowitz, J. (2006). "The Constancy of Ethics Admits the Changing World of Work". *Human Resource Management Review* (16), 245-268.
23. Marshall, C. (1992). School Administrators' Values: A Focus on Atypicals. *Educational Administration Quarterly* (28), 368-386.
24. Mengüşoğlu, T. (1965). Unchanged Values Changing Behaviors. A Critical Preparation for Philosophical Ethics. İstanbul: Publication of İstanbul University Faculty of Literature.
25. Ozankaya, Ö. (1999). Sociology. İstanbul: Cem Publications.
26. Özdevecioğlu, M. & Aksoy, M. S. (2005). Sabotage in Organizations: Types, Goals, Goals and Management. Cumhuriyet University, Journal of Economics and Administrative Sciences, 6 (1), 95-109.
27. Özkalp, E. (1995). Organizational Culture and Theoretical Developments. Anadolu University Open Education Faculty Journal, 1 (2), 60-71.
28. Pehlivan, İ. (2001). Managerial, Professional and Organizational Ethics. Ankara: Pegema Publishing House.
29. Pehlivan, İ. (1997). A Study on the Ethical Behaviors of Educational Administrators (The Case of Ankara Province) (Unpublished Doctoral Thesis). Ankara University, Ankara.
30. Pehlivan, İ. (1998). Managerial, Professional and Organizational Ethics. Ankara: Pegem Publications.

31. Richard, P. D. (1999). Help Wanted: Principals who Can Lead Professional Learning Communities. *NASSP Bulletin*, 83 (604), 10-19.
32. Taymaz, H. (2015). *Inspection, Concepts Principles Methods*. Ankara: Pegem Academy Publications.
33. Uğurlu, C. T. (2012). The Perceptions of Elementary School Teachers about Managerial Ethical Leadership Behavior. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 36 (2), 203-213.
34. Uğurlu, T. (2009). *The Impact of Managerial Ethical Leadership and Organizational Justice Behaviors on Elementary School Teachers' Organizational Commitment Levels*. Department of Educational Sciences Department of Educational Administration and Supervision (Unpublished Doctorate Thesis). Inonu University, Malatya.
35. Winter, P. A., Newton, R. M., & Kirkpatrick, R. L. (1998). The influence of work values on teacher selection decisions: The effects of principal values, teacher values, and principal-teacher value interactions. *Teaching and Teacher Education* (14), 385-400.
36. Yıldırım, A. & Şimşek, H. (2005). *Qualitative Research Methods in Social Sciences* (2. b.). Ankara: Seçkin Publications.
37. Yıldırım, A. & Şimşek, H. (2006). *Qualitative Research Methods in Social Sciences* (6. b.). Ankara: Seçkin Publishing.
38. Yıldırım, A. & Şimşek, H. (2011). *Qualitative Research Methods in Social Sciences* (8. b.). Ankara: Seçkin Publishing.
39. Yin, R. K. (1984). *Case study research: design and methods*. Beverly Hills: CA: Sage.

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